

THE COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGE GRAMMAR

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Introduction

Studies that compare languages provide insightful information about the distinctive qualities and grammatical structures of various languages. We will examine the grammatical distinctions between Uzbek, the official language of Uzbekistan, and English in this article. English and Uzbek share a number of grammatical parallels and distinctions, despite coming from different language families, which add to their unique linguistic traits.

Subject-Verb Concordance

Sentence construction that is grammatically accurate depends heavily on subject-verb agreement. Verb tenses in English have to match the number and person of their subjects. The sentence "He plays football every day," for example, appropriately pairs the singular subject "he" with the singular verb "plays." In the meantime, the plural verb "play" and the plural subject "they" match. Uzbek also uses subject-verb agreement. Sadullaev (1974) asserts that "Uzbek verbs undergo specific changes depending on the number and person of the subject." For instance, "I go" is translated as "Uzbek: Men ketaman" in English because the verb "ketaman" corresponds with the singular pronoun "men" (I).

Tenses in Comparison

Tenses are used in both Uzbek and English to convey information about time. The present, simple past, past participle, present perfect, present continuous, and past continuous are the six main tenses in English. With these tenses, speakers can express different temporal contexts in a single statement.

In a similar vein, Uzbek uses a variety of tenses to convey chronological connectedness. The Uzbek language has the present, simple past, future, and perfect

tenses, among others, according to Amanov (1981). Tenses in Uzbek are created by adding particular ends or by utilizing auxiliary verbs.

Word Sequence

English and Uzbek have different word orders, or how words are arranged in sentences. The word order in English is subject-verb-object (SVO), meaning that the subject usually comes before the verb and is followed by the object. As an illustration, "I (subject) like (verb) apples (object)." In contrast, Uzbek uses a subject-object-verb (SOV) word order.

The SOV word order is something that the Uzbek language inherited from its Turkic language family, according to Mirzamuhiddin and Takayama (2015). Uzbek differs from English and many other Indo-European languages in this particular trait.

Negative forms

Another place where Uzbek and English differ is in grammatical negation. When expressing negation in English, the word "not" is frequently used, as in "I am not going." On the other hand, Uzbek heavily uses suffixes.

Uzbek negates verbs, adjectives, and nouns with suffixes like "-may," "-mang," and "-mas," according to Kim (2009). "Uzbek: Men ketman" means "I go" in English, whereas "Uzbek: Men ketmayman" means "I do not go."

In summary

Despite being from different language families, Uzbek and English have some syntactic commonalities as well as unique linguistic characteristics. There are differences between their negation patterns, word ordering, tenses, and subject-verb agreement norms. We can appreciate the vast linguistic diversity and complexity of language structures found in our environment by recognizing their parallels and differences.

References

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